

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF A THERMOPLASTIC CROSS-PLY PREPREG FOR HELMET PREFORM MANUFACTURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper will discuss characterization of the temperature-dependent mechanical behaviors of Dyneema[®] HB80 to investigate the material for use in fabricating helmet preforms. Design of a radiant heating apparatus will also be discussed to minimize the temperature gradient across the specimen during experimental testing. A model of the cross-ply lamina will be generated using a hybrid discrete mesoscopic finite element approach and deep-draw forming of the material will be simulated. Properties measured from the characterization tests will be implemented into conventional beam and shell elements to capture the respective tensile and shear behaviors of the Dyneema[®] HB80 plies. Additional experimental trials will be conducted to further explore the material formability.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past, combat helmets have been manufactured from thermosetting polymer matrix composites (PMCs) [1]. While this material option has proven more effective than conventional metals, the mechanisms for energy absorption are not exceptionally efficient. In recent years, helmet design has advanced to enhance ballistic performance, i.e. to provide increased protection against penetration of ballistics and shrapnel. This improved function is accomplished through the use of thermoplastic matrices with continuous polymer fiber reinforcements. The combination of fiber strength and matrix flexibility makes thermoplastic PMCs a candidate material to offer efficient mechanisms for energy absorption and dissipation. The material considered specifically for this study is Dyneema[®] HB80, a [0/90]₂ cross-ply lamina comprised of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fibers consolidated in a thermoplastic polyurethane-based matrix.

The objective of the current research is to simulate the deep-draw forming of a helmet preform and, in future efforts, to model the subsequent compression molding of the final part. A simulation tool will be used to identify fiber orientations and to track changes in thickness, stress, and strain throughout the manufacturing process. These model outputs can potentially assist in determining what changes should be implemented, with regard to tooling design and processing conditions, in an effort to achieve a high-quality helmet preform. The accuracy of the simulation tool will be dependent on the quality of the material constants derived from characterization tests. The mechanical behavior of the thermoplastic cross-ply prepreg must therefore be characterized over a range of possible forming temperatures. This paper will focus on the methods associated with the lamina characterization for use as inputs to a finite element model.

2 MODELING APPROACH

Modeling of textile reinforcements can be challenging due to the multi-scale nature of the constituents. Ideally, modeling would be conducted on the fiber level (i.e., microscopic modeling). However, modeling on this level is too computationally taxing to analyze the forming of real parts and structures at the macro-scale. Therefore, this research employs a mesoscopic model (i.e., at the tow

level) using a discrete approach developed with a hypoelastic element description and an explicit formulation [2]. An explicit solver, chosen for its computational efficiency and robust contact algorithms, was determined to be more amenable to forming simulations than implicit solvers [2]. The ability of this modeling technique has already been demonstrated for a variety of fabric architectures including woven (e.g., plain-weave and twill-weave) and non-crimp fabrics (e.g., unidirectional and stitched) [3-9].

The fabric constituents are modeled using conventional elements present in commercial finite element software. The use of these standard elements makes the method attractive to industrial users. Linear beam elements are used to incorporate the tensile properties of the fibers, tows, rovings, or yarns while shell elements define the shear properties of the fabric. For example, a cross ply like the one shown in Figure 1 is discretized into a mixed-mesh grid where the unit cell consists of four beam elements and one shell element. The two parallel beam elements on the horizontal carry the properties of the 0° fibers, and the two parallel beam elements on the vertical embody the 90° fiber properties. The shell element has no tensile properties and is only allowed to deform via shear. User-defined material subroutines describe the mechanical behavior of the beam and shell elements for their respective contributions to the overall fabric behavior. Using this modeling technique, the simulation is able to capture the changing orientation of the fibers throughout the manufacturing process.

Figure 1: Beam/shell discrete mesoscopic hybrid finite element model

3 MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

The primary model inputs that will be implemented through a user defined material subroutine are the shear and tensile rigidities. Therefore the picture frame and standard tensile tests will be employed to measure the shear and tensile properties, respectively. However, because the material will have a temperature dependent response, an environmental chamber first needed to be developed in order to provide uniform heating during testing.

3.1 Experimental set-up for high temperature material characterization

Due to the thermoplastic nature of this material system, the fiber's ability to strain and the matrix's capacity to facilitate shear will both be temperature dependent. As forming temperature will affect several properties of the final composite part (including shrinkage, thickness variations, warping tendencies, and residual stresses) it is important to understand the material response as a function of temperature. Therefore, material characterization of this cross ply lamina will be performed over a range of possible forming temperatures, which will be facilitated by a heating apparatus mounted on the mechanical test machine.

There are three possible methods that can be used to heat the composite sheet: conduction, convection, and radiation. The first, conduction, requires direct contact of the source with the sink, which is not preferable as material is in motion during testing. Furthermore, conduction is an inefficient heating mechanism for polymers as they tend to behave like thermal insulators (i.e., have low thermal conductivity and diffusivity); therefore, the thermoplastic would have a substantial temperature gradient through the thickness and away from the point(s) of contact with the source. For these reasons, conductive heating is generally not used in industry for sheet forming applications [10].

The second option, convection, is more amenable because it is a non-contact method where thermal exchange occurs over a secondary medium. While not the fastest method, use of convection heating is occasionally seen in the composite forming industry when cycle times are not critical. Although, one benefit of using thermoplastic PMCs is the short processing times that facilitate high production rates,

which is generally a common objective when selecting this material system; therefore, the sheet should be brought up to temperature as quickly as possible [10]. Regardless, in an academic setting, the large time constant to reach steady state temperature is insignificant. The limiting factor with using convection heating in material characterization tests is creating a sealed environment. The heating apparatus will have openings at the top and bottom to accommodate gripping of the specimen during testing and, without a sealed environment, convection is highly inefficient.

As such, radiation was the method selected for this oven design. Like convection, it too is a non-contact method; however, radiation does not require a sealed environment. For this method, thermal exchange is implemented using electromagnetic waves that travel through space from a source to a target. The portion of the signal that is absorbed by the target will excite vibration of the material's atoms and the increased atomic motion results in heating of the specimen. Because air absorbs very little infrared energy, radiation is a fast and efficient means of heating polymer materials. For these reasons, radiation is the most commonly used heating method in composite forming applications [10].

Radiant heating will be accomplished for this research using infrared ceramic elements, chosen for their low initial and operating costs, good temperature control, and long service life [10]. The ceramics are commercially available in three profiles (Figure 2): convex, concave, and flat. While good for comfort heating, the dispersed radiation of wide area emitters (i.e., convex ceramics) is not appropriate for the design of this heating apparatus. Conversely, the concave ceramic elements produce concentrated radiant emission patterns, making them useful for spot heating. While panel arrays of these concave emitters can be designed to provide uniform heating over the sheet, as is done in most industrial applications, it is not practical for this oven design; due to spatial confinements for mounting on the Instron, the proper array pattern and source-to-sink proximity cannot be accommodated to uniformly heat the test sample in this manner. Therefore, flat-faced elements were selected for use since their surfaces offer a uniform radiant pattern to provide even heating at close proximity. A flat panel array was drafted and implemented in the oven (Figure 3).

Figure 2. (a) Concave, (b) flat, and (c) convex ceramic emitters [11]

Six square uniform ceramic elements ($12\text{ cm} \times 12\text{ cm}$) were purchased and fitted to the back wall of the oven. The elements were wired in parallel to achieve an equivalent temperature for all, and marginal spacing was left between the emitters to create an effectively continuous $50\text{ cm} \times 27\text{ cm}$ ceramic plate. Reflective insulation was adhered to the oven walls and circular holes were cut in the top and bottom surfaces to accommodate gripping of the test fixture. A feedback control system with a thermocouple sensor is used to regulate the temperature of ceramic elements. The approximate temperature of the test specimen can then be related to the source temperature using the Stefan Boltzmann Law. An additional thermocouple can also be used to monitor the temperature of the composite laminate. The resulting heating apparatus was mounted on the Instron machine (Figure 2b) and evaluated for its effectiveness.

Figure 3: (a) Infrared panel design and (b) implementation and mounting on Instron.

A sample specimen was secured in the rhombus rig within the oven and brought up to a temperature of approximately 90°C. Using an infrared (IR) camera, thermal images were taken to see the temperature gradient across the sample. Measurements queried at discrete locations (as indicated in Figure 4) yielded an average temperature of $89.7 \pm 2.5^\circ\text{C}$ over the area of interest, where the test specimen is in a state of pure shear. Overall, the new panel design was assessed to be sufficient for this research application.

Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)						
T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7
89.9	90.5	87.6	89.9	91.5	93.2	85.4

Figure 4: Thermal image of heated shear specimen.

3.2 Intra-ply Shear

Because extensibility of the UHMWPE fibers should be regulated to prevent tearing and maintain their mechanical properties, shear is facilitated as the main mode of deformation during preform manufacture. The in-plane shearing results in a change of angle between the 0° and 90° fibers. This fiber rotation allows the reinforcement to trellis such that it can conform to three-dimensional compound-curvatures. The lamina's resistance to shear is measured using the picture test method [12]. The equations in [12] relate measured crosshead's load and displacement to the specimen's shear

stress and strain. Because these equations assume all of the force is used to deform the central region of the specimen, any material interference outside this area must be either eliminated or accounted for. Therefore, to obtain an accurate measurement of the shear response, the matrix needs to be removed from the sample arms. Using acetone, the polyurethane-based matrix can be dissolved without damage to the fibers. In addition to the acetone, a fine-toothed comb assists in the removal of cross-fibers from the arms, leaving only loaded fibers in these areas (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Preparation and mounting of picture frame specimen.

Shear tests were performed on an Instron 4464 with a 2-kN load cell. The material was sheared at rates ranging between the minimum and maximum limits of the Instron. No difference in behavior was observed over these machine limits and, therefore, the material did not exhibit any viscoelastic response within the range studied (i.e., 3°/s – 11°/s). The laminas were also tested over the range of possible forming temperatures (70°C to 120°C). The results of this study, shown in Figure 6, follow the anticipated trend: as temperature increases, the material's resistance to shear decreases.

Figure 6: Temperature-dependent shear response of Dyneema® HB80.

3.3 Tension

The lamina was also tested in tension. A modified version of ASTM-D5035 was implemented in this research effort to obtain the elastic modulus as a function of temperature. Tensile tests were executed on an Instron 4464 using pneumatic grips with flat-faced jaws at a pressure of 620 kPa. Due to availability of resources, a 2-kN load cell was used (although a higher capacity cell was preferable). Because of the load limit, a ½ in sample width was chosen and the specimens were not able to be tested to failure at room temperature. However, only an accurate measurement of modulus was necessary for input to the model. Therefore, the 2-kN load cell was deemed sufficient.

A 16.5-in gage length was used to mitigate the influence of slippage. To improve gripping of the sample and to minimize slippage, ¼ in diameter steel pins were used outside the jaws. The specimen was mounted such that the sample came through the grips, around the pin, and then back through the grips (see Figure 7). The face of the sample in contact with the jaw surfaces had fibers oriented in the loaded direction while the face of the sample in contact with the pin had fibers oriented in the cross direction.

Figure 7: Tensile test setup

Tests were performed across the machine limits (i.e., crosshead displacement speeds spanning ½ in/min to 20 in/min). Statistically insignificant variance in tensile modulus was observed over the machine limits, indicating there is effectively no rate dependence over the range tested. Using a crosshead speed of 4 in/min, five samples were tested at each temperature, ranging from 70°C to 120°C in 10°C increments. The apparent modulus of the lamina was plotted as a function of temperature for the warp and weft specimens tested (Figure 8). The trend best follows a third order polynomial over the range of temperatures studied and no appreciable difference was observed between 0° and 90° directions.

Figure 8. Apparent modulus as a function of temperature with a polynomial fit

A representative data set is plotted for each temperature tested (Figure 9). Trends can be spotted that, with an increase in temperature, there is a: (1) decrease in modulus, (2) reduction in yield strength/strain, and (3) increase in ductility. A summary of apparent modulus and yield point for each temperature is presented in Table 1. Note that no yield values are provided for room temperature (i.e., 20°C) or 50°C because the load limit was exceeded before yield.

Figure 9. Representative data for varying temperature

	Apparent Modulus [GPa]			Yield Strength [MPa]			Yield Strain [%]		
	Average	±	Stdev	Average	±	Stdev	Average	±	Stdev
20°	44.4	±	0.2	-----	±	-----	-----	±	-----
50°	32.2	±	1.5	-----	±	-----	-----	±	-----
70°	27.0	±	0.9	669	±	26	3.98%	±	0.25%
80°	25.5	±	1.0	604	±	24	3.82%	±	0.29%
90°	25.2	±	0.3	592	±	11	3.90%	±	0.07%
100°	21.9	±	1.0	435	±	6	3.15%	±	0.08%
110°	18.9	±	0.6	310	±	14	2.74%	±	0.19%
120°	14.4	±	0.4	192	±	9	2.20%	±	0.10%

Table 1: Summary of tensile results as a function of temperature

4 FORMING TRIALS

With the mechanical behaviors characterized and understood, the material properties can be implemented into the finite element model. The preliminary forming trials are performed on a hemispherical geometry. As the cross-ply shears to conform to the double-curvature, the fibers will begin to stack on top of each other, thereby locally increasing the ply thickness. This thickness change is especially pronounced at high degrees of shear. For example, one ply of Dyneema® HB80 formed to a hemisphere geometry will exhibit a shear contour like that shown in Figure 10. If the thickness variation for the same shear profile is plotted over the undeformed ply geometry, the resulting contour is shown in Figure 11a. The ply thickness increases by up to 50% in some locations. Such stepping of the thickness with result in uneven consolidation pressures over the preform during compression molding and will adversely affect the ballistic performance of the helmet. Therefore filler plies will be employed to assist in creating a uniform thickness. These filler plies, like that shown in Figure 11b, will be darted to remove material in locations that will thicken on the full plies.

Figure 10. Degree of shear necessary for cross-ply to conform to hemisphere geometry

In addition to providing thickness contours that can aid in choosing filler fly geometries, the model has the potential to assist in selecting processing conditions. Traditionally, this is accomplished with parametric studies, which can be costly and time consuming. Using a simulation tool can be more efficient in investigating and isolating the effects of each processing parameter. For example, if excessive wrinkling manifests during the forming process (Figure 12a), manufacturing conditions such as binder pressure, punch velocity, forming temperature, and blank size can be varied in the finite element model to find a suitable combination that mitigates the problem (Figure 12b).

Figure 11. (a) Contour of thickness change from the nominal sheet value of 0.148 mm plotted on the undeformed lamina and (b) potential darted filler ply pattern

Figure 12. Hemispheres formed with (a) excessive and (b) minimal wrinkling

5 CONCLUSIONS

Characterizations of the temperature-dependent mechanical behaviors of Dyneema[®] HB80 were presented as part of an investigation into the material for use in helmet fabrication. Shear frame experiments and tensile testing were performed over a range of possible temperatures used in the preforming process. The material was observed to be less compliant to shear loading at lower temperatures and more compliant at higher temperatures. Furthermore, results of the tensile tests showed that there was a decrease in modulus, reduction in yield strength/strain, and increase in ductility as temperature increased. A finite element model of Dyneema[®] HB80 was presented based on the experimentally determined properties. This model will be used to simulate the complete helmet manufacturing process.

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